

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MANAGEMENT PSYCHOLOGY IN SYSTEM OF PUBLIC HEALTH SERVICES: THE COMPETENCE APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17533494>

Abstract

This article analyzes the importance of psychological knowledge in communication between physicians and patients, physicians and nurses, and relationships with colleagues. The object of study is the professional interaction of various categories of medical personnel with patients. We examine the essence of a competency-based approach in modern HR management and explore emotional intelligence as an organizational and psychological category. The results of the management styles of physicians who are line and top managers are analyzed. Training in the psychology of human relations, as an important area of management and a component of the management system, plays a primary role.

Keywords: healthcare system, organizational psychology, management style, management competencies, block management systems, human relations, psychological qualities of a leader.

Background. Modern management operates in various areas, including the study of human relationships. Knowledge of psychology is of primary importance not only in the healthcare system but also especially for management professionals. Managing a production or organization requires knowledge of personnel management and the ability to formulate HR policies. Currently, along with improving existing teaching methods, the introduction of psychological knowledge (communicative competence and the psychology of communication) as a management area in healthcare is very important.

An analysis of studies devoted to the competency-based approach to assessing a subject's readiness to solve professional problems indicates that various aspects of this problem are being most intensively studied in the context of the development of modern concepts of general and vocational education. [4, p. 21] Studies of the work effectiveness of experienced professionals and their readiness for changing job positions and professional conditions, particularly in medicine and the healthcare system as a whole, from a competency-based approach are few, despite the fact that the relevance of studying this important organizational and psychological resource for improving the effectiveness of medical care is beyond doubt. In this regard, it is particularly important for both employers and managers to understand the specific invariants of basic management competencies. As noted in a number of studies in organizational psychology, fostering employee initiative,

a desire for success, the ability to attract and retain professionals, and the ability to operate at high standards are essential components of effective management, which are also core competencies of management personnel. [7, p. 27] Basic, or general, competencies define organizational requirements for professionals working in a specific job position, in this case, management corresponding to a line or senior (top management) position. Professional knowledge and experience constitute so-called threshold competencies, specific to specific professional fields, in this case, medicine.

The success of an individual's work in the public and professional spheres depends on their communication skills (physicians, mid-level and junior medical professionals, and social workers). In this regard, there is a real need in modern society for specialists capable of developing their personal qualities, spirituality, and professionalism, who are able to maximize their natural abilities and develop a general and communicative culture. The need for collaboration between medicine and psychology has become clear, not only in disease prevention, examination, treatment, and patient rehabilitation, but also, more importantly, in joint management [3, c.496]. The goal of the study is to develop in students an understanding of the importance of knowledge about communicative competence and the psychology of human relations and its subsequent implementation in their practical work.

Material and Methods.

Training in communicative competence and the psychology of human relations—as important areas of

management, forming a component of the management system—plays a primary role.

There are a number of interaction models based on:

Communication models within the principles of synergistic interaction in the "doctor-nurse" system were discussed with mid-level healthcare workers in terms of the principle of a clear delineation of functions, focusing more on partnership than on "bring-and-serve" or "do what the doctor says," which devalues the nurse's experience and inhibits her initiative and independent thinking.

The principle of partnership. The nurse should have a certain degree of autonomy. Of course, she shouldn't write out medical orders on her own, but she should be able to independently vary her behavior depending on the situation. Ideally, the nurse should work in "anticipatory reflection," that is, interact with the doctor as if she were reading his next action or instruction without words. Nurses should also demonstrate initiative, which can be demonstrated by seeking to improve their manual skills, as well as a certain resourcefulness and speed of work. [4, p. 24]

Communication models in the "Patient-Doctor" system jointly analyzed patient personality traits: temperament, character, abilities, intelligence, etc., which the physician must consider when establishing psychological rapport with the patient. The main tactic is establishing an emotional connection with patients and then moving on to the informational aspects of the conversation. [2, p. 47] During practical training, situational problems were solved, and the algorithm of actions of the physician, nurse, and social worker was analyzed with categories such as "anxious patient." Physician communication tactics: the physician should seek the help of a clinical psychologist. "Distrustful patient" patients: such patients approach the treatment process skeptically and with caution. Physician communication tactics: the physician should first begin treatment by overcoming the patient's barriers of mistrust and alienation. Patient suggestions. This type of patient is trying to get attention, just like doctors.

Communication Models in the "With Colleagues" Relationship System. In this model of relationships with colleagues, physicians are required to demonstrate honesty, fairness, kindness, integrity, respect for the knowledge and experience of their colleagues, and a willingness to selflessly share their experience and knowledge.

Physicians must do everything in their power to create a favorable moral and psychological climate in the workforce, actively participate in the work of the medical association, protect the honor and dignity of their colleagues, and prevent the medical practice of dishonest and incompetent colleagues, as well as unprofessionals who are detrimental to the health of patients. Physicians are obligated to treat mid-level and junior medical personnel with due respect and to facilitate the improvement of their professional knowledge and skills.

Recently, a number of studies have affirmed the high importance of emotional intelligence in terms of

basic management competencies [7, p. 15]. These abilities are divided into four groups, with each group comprising four core abilities, each with different prerequisites. Thus, Group I includes the acquisition and recognition of emotional information and comprises the most basic skills related to the emotional sphere: perception, evaluation, and expression of emotion. These elementary perceptual processes are necessary prerequisites for the further processing of emotional information. Group II describes ways of using emotions to stimulate the thought process ("emotional facilitation of thinking") and identifies various emotional events that facilitate the intellectual processing of information. Group III includes the ability to understand and analyze emotions. It is represented by abilities that determine abstract understanding and thinking about emotions. Their range extends from the ability to name emotions and recognize connections between words and emotions themselves to the conscious ability to move from one emotion to another. It can be assumed that this component of EI is closest to executive intelligence, considered as "an individual's ability to most rationally use received information as a prerequisite for an idea or as a guide to action" [6, p. 27].

Group IV encompasses an individual's ability to manage their own and others' emotions in order to stimulate emotional and intellectual growth. This integral quality implies the possession of the most developed personal skills, ranging from the ability to remain open to feelings—both pleasant and unpleasant—to the ability to manage emotions in oneself and others, enhancing pleasant emotions and mitigating unpleasant ones. This group of higher-order abilities represents the interweaving of many factors, including motivational, emotional, and cognitive, which must be recognized and balanced to successfully manage and cope with feelings.

In medicine, leaders are typically experienced physicians, professionals, and individuals with a well-established professional position and professional identity. However, the potential of managerial competencies in the selection and placement of management personnel is little known. Scientific approaches to assessing this potential have not been developed. A change in professional status entails not only the emergence of additional professional functions and responsibilities for the individual. It also requires the development of a set of psychological and personal qualities that determine successful management. Differentiating these characteristics from a competency-based approach, based on scientifically proven criteria, in particular those defining the structure of emotional intelligence and its relationship with the most effective management styles, can enable employers to more purposefully build line and top management teams in healthcare institutions of various profiles and statuses. Thus, it is obvious that consideration of the subjective characteristics of a physician-manager from the standpoint of a competence-based approach can become the basis for identifying a subject "field" of management in the healthcare system, which, in turn, will make it possible to make the training of professionals to perform management functions more effective.

Conclusions.

Approaching management psychology from a competency-based approach allows us to identify the components of management competencies and establish their variability for top and line management in the healthcare system. This approach allows us to identify "targets" for developmental interventions. For top management, these include empathic abilities, skills for reflecting on one's own emotional states and experiences, emotional awareness, and attention to staff. For line management, these include skills for self-regulation of emotional states and the ability to recognize the emotions of others and manage them in the best interests of the organization.

These results can serve as a basis for defining organizational and psychological foundations for improving the effectiveness of physician training for management functions.

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